

Paracas textiles – Colour and condition. Investigation of the mordants and state of degradation of the Paracas textile collections in Peru and Sweden

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ABSTRACT

During the course of the repatriation of a collection of Paracas textiles from Sweden to Peru, an investigation of the textiles' physical conditions and a study of their colourant auxiliaries were undertaken. Conservators from the National Museums of World Culture, Sweden and the National Museum of Archaeology, Anthropology and History, Peru collaborated with the Heritage Laboratory of the Swedish National Heritage Board. The analytical techniques used were: fibre documentation, optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy/energy-dispersive x-ray analysis, compression testing, pH measurements and micro-x-ray fluorescence mapping. Results suggest that colourants and their auxiliaries, such as mordants, cause greater differences in condition than past storage environments or treatments.

BACKGROUND

Gothenburg has an important collection of 2000-year-old textiles from the Paracas peninsula in Peru. They were excavated and taken to Sweden during the 1930s, and some pieces were displayed until the late 1980s (Paul 1979). Investigation by Ekroth-Edebo in 1990 led to concerns about their condition; the textiles were deemed too acidic. Thus an ammonia gas deacidification method was implemented in 1994 by the Swedish Institute for Textile Research (TEFO) (Åsnes 1990–1994, Javér 2002).

In 2008, the collection was exhibited in *A Stolen World*, an exhibition which aimed to raise awareness of the consequences of looted cultural heritage (National Museum of World Culture 2009). A year later, Peru asked for repatriation. Negotiations between the City of Gothenburg and the Peruvian Ministry of Culture determined that ownership of the textiles would be returned to Peru (Hulthén and Hoffman 2012).

Faced with the realities of arranging the safe transfer of objects like the Paracas textiles, the conservators from the National Museums of World Culture (NMWC) had to develop new forms of packing and transportation, while the conservators from the National Museum of Archaeology, Anthropology and History (NMAAH) in Lima, Peru had to make space in their storage facilities for 89 large textiles. The first four textiles were repatriated in 2014 (Figure 1). A year later, Anna Javér returned to MNAAH and, with Carmen Thays Delgado and Maria Ysabel Medina Castro, examined the physical condition of the textiles (Javér 2016).

AIMS

The aims of the project were to investigate and compare the condition of Paracas textiles held under various museum environments, in Sweden and in Peru, to study the influence of the ammonia treatment that was carried out in the 1990s and to compare the results to those obtained during previous investigations from the 1990s onwards. In addition, it was hoped that the investigations might further our knowledge of the mordants used in these ancient textiles as there is still a large knowledge gap about the colourant systems used by the ancient Andean cultures (Price et al. 2015).

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Figure 1. The four textiles repatriated in June 2014. Calendar mantle (RT-38072, MNAAH/1935.32.0179, NMWC); Bird mantle (RT-38073, MNAAH/1935.32.0190, NMWC); Bird tunic (RT-38074, MNAAH/1935.32.0188, NMWC); and fragment (RT-38075, MNAAH/1935.32.0213, NMWC). Photo: Hannes Anderzén/NMWC (CC BY)

SAMPLING

Thirty-four thread samples were taken from 12 Paracas textiles from the MNAAH and NMWC. Most were ca. 10 mm long, with some shorter and some longer (up to 35 mm). Weights varied between 0.0001–0.0015 g. All but two samples were S spun, 2z-ply. The samples comprised 1 red and 13 brown and black cotton threads, 1 black thread of mixed cotton and camelid fibres and 19 camelid threads: 1 grey, 3 white, 3 blue, 4 yellow and 8 red. Unfortunately, it was not possible to sample the same range of colours from all textiles (Table 1).

The three fragments (1935.32.0211; 1935.32.0212; 1935.32.0213) for micro-x-ray fluorescence (XRF) mapping were chosen where the embroidery contained the widest range of colours in close proximity in order to minimise the area of mapping. Where possible, areas of lost embroidery with exposed ground weave were included in the mapping area.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Compression tests

Samples were supported on glass microscope slides. One-mm sections were cut from each sample, ensuring that the yarn's twist and ply were not disturbed. A 2 × 2 cm microscope slide cover glass was placed on the sample and then weighted with a 200-gram weight. Stereomicroscope images of the samples were recorded before and after compression. The samples' behaviour, e.g. how flexible the fibres were or how easily they crushed under the weight, was noted.

Micro pH measurements

For every sample, approximately 4 mm of thread was put into a 0.5 ml Eppendorf safe-lock micro centrifuge tube and covered with 50 µl of deionised water. Three blanks were added using just deionised water.

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Table 1. Sampling of Paracas fibres

Object	Identification numbers		Sample information						
	Sample		Embroidery	Ground weave	Camelid	Cotton	Colour	Spin /ply	NH ₃ treatment
RT-02931 mantel	MNAAHP 001		x		x		red	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 002			x		x	brown	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 003		x		x		white	S(2z)	
RT-01683 mantel	MNAAHP 004		x		x		blue	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 005			x		x	brown	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 006a		x		x		white	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 006b		x		x		grey	S(2z)	
RT-39346 border	MNAAHP 007			x		x	red	S(2z)	
RT-02649 fragment	MNAAHP 008		x		x		yellow	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 009		x		x		red	S(2z)	
	MNAAHP 010		x		x		blue	S(2z)	
1935.32.0198 border	NMWC NH ₃ 001		x		x		yellow	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 002			x		x	brown	S(2z)	x
1935.32.0211a fragment	NMWC NH ₃ 003		x		x		yellow	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 004			x		x	brown	S(2z)	x
1935.32.0211c fragment	NMWC 005		x		x		yellow	S(2z)	
	NMWC 006			x		x	brown	S(2z)	
1935.32.0205 poncho	NMWC NH ₃ 007		x		x		red	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 008			x		x	brown	S(2z)	x
1935.32.0085 tunic	NMWC NH ₃ 009		x		x		red	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 010			x		x	brown	S(2z)	x
(1935.32.0179) RT-38072 mantle	NMWC NH ₃ 011		x		x		white	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 012			x		x	brown	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 013		x		x		blue	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 014			x		x	brown	Z(2s)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 015		x		x		red	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 016			x		x	brown	Z(2s)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 017		x		x		red	S(2z)	x
	NMWC NH ₃ 018		x		x	x	black	S(2z)	x
1935.32.0190 mantel	NMWC 019		x		x		red	S(2z)	
	NMWC 020			x		x	black	S(2z)	
1935.32.0188 poncho	NMWC 021		x		x		red	S(2z)	
	NMWC 022			x		x	black	S(2z)	
	NMWC 023			x		x	brown	S(2z)	

The samples were agitated in an ultrasonic bath for 20 min, then left to extract at room temperature for approximately 6 hours. Measurements were taken with a new Horiba LAQUA twin pH meter calibrated with a pH 7.0 standard buffer solution. The pH meter probe was rinsed with ample deionised water between each measurement (but not dried in order not to disturb the sensitive probe surfaces).

SEM/EDS

Fibres taken from short pieces (1–2 mm) of the thread samples were mounted on conductive carbon tape and gold sputtered using a Quorum Q150R ES set to a 6 nm thickness. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were taken at various magnifications using a LEO 1455 VP SEM.

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Specific instrumental settings were recorded on each image. Energy-dispersive x-ray (EDS) spectra were collected from uncoated samples mounted on carbon tape. Using an Oxford Instruments EDS with INCA 400 software, the following settings were used: accelerating voltage of 20 keV, working distance of 15 mm, high vacuum, 50 s live time.

Micro-XRF

Elemental maps were collected from the three woven and embroidered textile fragments using a Bruker micro-XRF Artax 800 equipped with a molybdenum x-ray tube set to 50 kV and 600 µA and with a poly capillary lens giving a spot size of 60–70 µm. Helium flushing was employed for three maps in order to enhance the detection of light elements. Table 2 lists all variable settings.

Table 2. Micro-XRF elemental maps

Variable settings	1935.32.0211	1935.32.0212	1935.32.0212	1935.32.0213	1935.32.0213
	map 1	map 1	map 2	map 1	map 2
Helium flushing	yes	no	yes	yes	no
Scan live time	8 s	8 s	8 s	10 s	8 s
Spot distance	0.25 mm	0.18 mm	0.25 mm	0.25 mm	0.2 mm
Scan area	21.2 × 17 mm	32.5 × 3.5 mm	10.5 × 3.5 mm	26 × 5.5 mm	14 × 7.5 mm
Measurement points	5885	3620	645	2398	6461
Total scan time	23:37 h	14:04 h	02:30 h	15 h	25:07 h

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Previous investigations and ammonia treatment (1990–2001)

In 1990, TEFO researchers measured the pH of 42 fibre samples from 24 textiles by placing a few mm of thread onto pH paper and wetting the thread with deionised water (Åsnes 1990). The pH paper readings of the camelid fibres suggested that they were highly acidic with pH levels between 2.9 and 3.4 and one cotton thread with a pH of 2.8. The same year, the team of researchers investigated comparable Paracas textiles in Peru at the NMAAH. Fourteen samples from eight textiles in the collection in Peru were also assessed as highly acidic using the same pH paper method (measuring camelid fibres between pH 2.8–4.7). The unpublished report on the NMWC also includes SEM images of several of the samples and a subjective assessment of the samples' strength and flexibility.

Following this investigation, approximately half of the Gothenburg Paracas collection in 1994 underwent a deacidification treatment in specially designed glass cases that had been temporarily filled with ammonia gas that was then flushed with nitrogen (Åsnes 1990 and 1994). In 2000, the exhibition in Gothenburg was closed. In 2001, the collection was removed from the glass cases and housed in the new storage facilities at the NMWC (Javér 2012). When the cases were opened, the ammonia gas concentration was over 200 ppm; the textiles had remained in an ammonia atmosphere for six years despite flushing the cases with nitrogen (Javér 2002). At that time, a researcher from the Swedish Institute for Fibre and Polymer Technology (IFP) carried out a small-scale pH and handling assessment

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of the textiles treated with ammonia gas and those that had remained untreated in storage; the treatment was deemed successful for camelid fibres but raised questions about the condition of the cotton fibres (Ohlsson 2001). Because ammonia gas is considered a temporary alkaliser that does not leave an alkaline reserve (Petherbridge 1987), it is doubtful that the raised pH Ohlsson observed for the camelid fibres was actually durable. Changes in dyeing properties for wool fibres treated with ammonia gas have been reported (Lee 2003), suggesting that ammonia gas can open the physical structure of wool fibres to allow greater diffusion. It is unknown how lasting these effects are on such ancient fibres, especially as they had been exposed for so many years. Conservators are worried about the long-term impact of this treatment.

Compression tests

Figure 2 shows examples of the compression tests. Table 3 gives a summary of all the results. Differences in condition do not appear to be related to where the textiles have been kept or whether or not they underwent a deacidification treatment, but are rather correlated with certain colours. Several of the 2000-year-old fibres are still flexible and supple, in particular the white and grey ones, presumably undyed, and the blue-dyed camelid fibres. Some black and red camelid fibres from the embroidery and many of the brown cotton fibres from the ground weave fabrics were crushed under the weight of the compression test. This brittleness, apparently caused by specific colourants, had been noted previously as ‘carbonised’ fibres (Ekroth-Edebo 1990, Peters 2012).

Table 3 also includes fibre condition assessments that derive from notes taken during the previous investigations in 1990 and 2001 (Åsnes 1992, Ohlsson 2001). The notes refer to observations from sample handling and visual inspections, but they resemble the results from the 2014 and 2016 compression tests.

Figure 2. Compression test. Red (very brittle) and white (no damage) camelid yarn sample before and after compression test. Photo: RAÄ/NMWC (CC BY)

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Table 3. Results of the compression test

	Cotton	Camelid
MNAAHP 2016		3 of 9 flexible/strong (2 white, 1 grey)
	2 of 2 fraying/weak (1 red 2 brown)	3 of 9 fraying/weak (2 blue, 1 yellow)
		2 of 9 very fragile (red)
MNAAHP 1994 (Åsnes 1994)	2 of 4 flexible/strong (white)	1 of 10 flexible/strong (yellow)
	1 of 4 fraying/weak (brown)	5 of 10 fraying/weak (yellow, 2 red, 2 black)
	1 of 4 very fragile (white)	4 of 10 very fragile (2 black, 2 red,)
NMWC 2014	1 of 4 flexible/strong (black)	
	1 of 4 fraying/weak (black)	1 of 3 fraying/weak (yellow)
	2 of 4 very fragile (brown)	2 of 3 very fragile (red)
NMWC NH ₃ 2014	3 of 7 flexible/strong (brown)	2 of 9 flexible/strong (1 white, 1 blue)
	3 of 7 fraying/weak (brown)	5 of 9 fraying/weak (2 yellow, 3 red)
	1 of 7 very fragile (brown)	2 of 9 very fragile (1 red, 1 black)
IFP 2001 NH ₃ (Ohlsson 2001)		
	2 of 3 fraying/weak (red)	11 of 16 fraying/weak (1 yellow, 3 red, 3 black, 4?)
	1 of 3 very fragile (brown)	5 of 16 very fragile (2 black, 3 red)
IFP 2001 (Ohlsson 2001)		
	1 of 1 very fragile (brown)	2 of 2 fraying/weak (yellow)
IFP 1990-1993 (Åsnes 1990, 1993)		
	2 of 2 fraying/weak (red)	7 of 8 fraying/weak (4 ?, 2 red, 1 yellow)
MME 1990 (Ekroth-Edebo 1990)		4 of 8 flexible/strong (2 white, 2 blue)
		2 of 8 fraying/weak (2 yellow, 1 red)
	2 of 2 very fragile (1 brown, 1 black)	2 of 8 very fragile (1 red, 1 black)

Figure 3. The pH measurement results for camelid and cotton samples plotted against the compression test assessments

Micro pH measurements

The blanks were measured between samples and showed pH levels of 5.7, 5.9 and 6.3, which is consistent with expected pH results for deionised water but also indicates an uncertainty level of approximately ± 0.3.

The camelid samples' pH range was 3.7–6.6 with an average pH of 4.5, while the cotton samples' pH range was 4.8–6.5 with an average pH of 5.4. There were no notable correlations between pH values and compression test assessments or sample groups or colours. As such, pH tests are a poor indicator for assessing differences in the degradational state of textiles (Figure 3). However, it is important to know that the pH values of the tested textiles are considered below the acceptable ranges in terms of stability for both the cotton and camelid fibres (Tímár-Balázs and Eastop 1998), although they do not appear as low as suggested by Åsnes (1990) or Ohlsson (2001). Their pH measurements relied on the relatively subjective method of judging the colour differences of pH paper after it had been in contact with wetted fibres. The results of the current study cast doubt on these previous assessments on which the decision to undertake a quite drastic deacidification treatment was based.

SEM/EDS

The SEM investigations of the surface morphology of both camelid and cotton fibres showed that fibre condition varied greatly within the same

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Figure 4. SEM images of a blue camelid fibre (left) and a brown cotton fibre (right) from Mantle RT-01683, showing brittleness and cracking. Photos: RAÄ/NMWC (CC BY)

textile, even within the same sample. It is possible to observe examples of severe fibre degradation mixed in with fibres that look pristine (Figure 4). This is consistent with observations and SEM images taken during the 1990 and 2001 studies. Some typical signs of degradation that were observed on camelid fibres included loss of scales, perpendicular and longitudinal cracks, and fragmented fibre pieces with sharp break edges. Some black camelid fibres had almost no scales left and broke into small pieces with sharp ends. Surface debris was observed on many samples, both cotton and camelid, although overall the cotton samples appeared more soiled than the camelid fibres. Typical signs of damage on cotton fibres included cracking in seemingly random and sometimes bifurcated direction and, occasionally, loss of the cotton fibre cuticle, primary wall and winding layers exposing the fibrillar structure of the secondary wall.

EDS analysis has yielded interesting but at times inconclusive results. The elemental analysis indicates the presence of sodium, aluminium, silicon, chlorine, potassium and calcium on most fibres (Table 4). Phosphorous was detected on some, but not all, cotton fibres. Iron was consistently detected only on one sample, the black mixed cotton and camelid fibres from the Calendar mantle (Figure 1), which is very fragile. Magnesium was only detected on a black cotton sample that is still flexible and strong and has a pH of 6.7, perhaps indicating that the magnesium acted as a protective alkaline buffer.

Surface debris on both cotton and camelid samples was shown to contain high levels of calcium.

Aluminium, potentially present as a mordant, was identified in several dyed fibre samples but not coherently for samples of the same colour. Also, aluminium was sometimes identified on cotton samples and on grey camelid even though they were presumably undyed and should therefore not contain any mordant. As alum is the most important textile mordant, its presence (or absence) in these ancient textiles would be fascinating to prove. Since Peru has natural resources of alum salts (Rosario-Chirinos 1999), it is tempting to assume that they were employed in the highly advanced textile culture of the ancient Paracas civilisation. However, this has not been possible to firmly establish analytically.

Micro-XRF results

The micro-XRF mapping yielded surprisingly good results with a wider than expected range of elements clearly associated with differently coloured areas in the textiles. Many of the detected elements are likely to have been used as mordants or dye bath auxiliaries. Mordants in dyed textiles are notoriously difficult to analyse and very little such work has been carried out on textiles from ancient Andean cultures (Ekroth-Edebo 1990, Summerour 2013). Chlorine, potassium, calcium, manganese, iron, copper and zinc were clearly mapped on all three textile fragments (Figures 5–7). Nickel and strontium were less clear but still yielded reasonable maps for two of the fragments. Several other elements, including aluminium, were detected, and are marked in the accumulated spectra (Figure 8), but their maps showed no specific distribution and they were therefore not included in the summary of results (Table 5).

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The overlay of the accumulated spectra (Figure 8) showed that the range of elements that were detected at medium to high levels are present at overall comparable relative quantities on all five maps collected. The interpretation of each individual element map is summarised in Table 5, which reveals some interesting similarities but also disparities among similar colours on the three fragments.

Table 4. Results of EDS analysis

Identification numbers		Sample information			EDS results										
Object	Sample	camelid	cotton	colour	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cl	K	Ca	Ti	Fe
RT-02931 mantel	MNNAHP 001	x		red	+		++	+		++			+		
	MNNAHP 002		x	brown	+		++	+	+	+		+	++		
	MNNAHP 003	x		white				+		+++	+				
RT-01683 mantel	MNNAHP 004	x		blue	+		+	+		++	+		+		
	MNNAHP 005		x	brown	++			+		++	+	+	+		
				surface debris	++		+	+		++	+	+	++		
	MNNAHP 006a	x		white	+			+		+++	+	+	+		
				surface debris	+		+	+		++	+		+		
	MNNAHP 006b	x		grey	++		+	+		++	+	+			
RT-39346 border	MNNAHP 007 (border)		x	red	+		++	++	+	+	+	+			
					+		++	+	+	+	+				
RT-02649 fragment	MNNAHP 008	x		yellow	+		+	+		++	+	+			
	MNNAHP 009	x		red			++	+		+++					
					+		++	+	+	+++					
MNNAHP 010	x			blue	+		+	+		++	+	+			
					+		+	+		+++	+	+	+		
1935.32.0179 mantel	PAR-018	x	x	black						+++					+
						++	+		+++		+	+		+	
					+		+		++		+	+		+	
					+				+++			+		+	
1935.32.0190 mantel	PAR-020		x	black	+		+	++	+	+	+	+	++	+	+++
					+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
					+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
					+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
					+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+		
					++	++	++	+	+	++	++	++	+		
				surface debris	++	+	+	+		+	++	++	+++		
					++	+	+	+		+	++	++	+++		

Each row in the EDS results represents the analyses taken on separate fibres within the sample. Semi-quantitative assessments were made relative to the oxygen peak in each spectrum.
+++ : large peak (≥ half oxygen peak)
++ : small to medium peak (≤ half oxygen peak)
+ : peak near background level

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Table 5. Summary of results of micro-XRF mapping showing element distribution by colour

Object	No.	Colour	Cl	K	Ca	Mn	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	Sr
1935.32.0211 map 1	1	white	3000			4000	79000		900	3600	
	11	beige									
	5	grey									
	8	tan									
	2	yellow			13300					1800	
	7	brown		20600							
	13	brown							1800		
	3	brown	1500								
	4	red									
	6	pink									
	9	pink									
	14	red									
	15	red									
	10	blue		10300							
	12	black			26600	7500	157800				
	16	brown (ground weave)									
	17	yellow									
1935.32.0212 map 1	1	yellow			14000	1800	55000		2700	1900	300
	2	yellow							5500		
	3	pink	700								
	4	red									
	5	blue	1500	11000						3400	
	6	brown		23000	28000	3500	109000	400			500
	7	black						800			
	8	black									
	9	black									
1935.32.0212 map 2	1	yellow			9800		10200			1400	
	2	yellow					20000				
	3	pink	700						4900		
	9	brown	1400	9300	19500						
	10	brown (ground weave)		18300					2500	700	
1935.32.0213 map 1	4	grey		4300			125000	610	1400	5100	
	1	yellow			20400	5200	62500			2600	
	5	red	1500								
	3	pink		8600				1200			
	9	blue	2900								
	6	black									
	7	black							2800		
	8	black (eye)			40900	10400					
12	red/yellow										
1935.32.0213 map 2	1	grey		3200				500	800	5100	
	2	grey/red (1 ply of each)				7500	65100				700
	3	yellow			20100					2500	
	4	yellow	700								
	5	pink						1000			
	6	red							1600		
	10	red									
	9	blue	1400								
7	black										
8	black (eye)		6300	40100	15100	130100				1400	

Note: Each element on each map was regarded separately with white representing the highest detected levels, grey representing intermediate levels and black representing the lowest levels, or absence. The highest and lowest measured spectral net peak areas are marked in the table.

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Figure 5. Micro-XRF mapping area of fragment 1932.32.0211 (map 1). Photo: Ina Marie Winther Ashaug/NMWC (CC BY)

Figure 6. Micro-XRF elemental maps of fragment 1935.32.0211. Photos: Ina Marie Winther Ashaug/NMWC (CC BY)

Figure 7. Micro-XRF mapping areas of fragment 1932.32.0212 map 1 (top) and map 2 (middle right) and of fragment 1932.32.0213 map 1 (bottom right) and map 2 (bottom left). Photos: Ina Marie Winther Ashaug/NMWC (CC BY)

Figure 8. Micro-XRF accumulated spectra (note that molybdenum and argon derive from the instrumental setup)

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Chlorine was strongest in the blue areas, while iron, magnesium, potassium, calcium and strontium were often associated with browns and blacks. Copper appears to have been a common mordant for red and pink, but also some yellows and browns and black. Zinc was mostly detected in light-coloured areas of grey, white and beige. Nickel was found in one pink and one black area. The detection of inorganic components in threads that were previously deemed undyed may imply batch mordanting for threads that were left undyed or the use of now-faded fugitive dyes.

CONCLUSION

Micro-XRF mapping revealed a wide range of potential mordants and dye auxiliaries. Chlorine, potassium, calcium, manganese, iron, nickel, copper, zinc and strontium were all shown to be associated with certain colours in the textiles. While aluminium, silicon, phosphorous, sulfur, titanium, arsenic, mercury and lead were detected with diffuse distribution.

EDS indicated the presence of sodium, aluminium, silicon, chlorine, potassium and calcium on most fibres, whilst magnesium, phosphorous, titanium and iron were detected on a few samples only. The EDS results could not replicate the micro-XRF mapping results which may be due to the surface sensitivity of the analytical technique.

The SEM investigations showed that fibre condition can vary greatly within one textile and even within one sample. Signs of damage, such as fibre cracking, surface debris, loss of camelid scales and cotton cuticle, were all observed but not always coherently with the assessments of sample condition made by compression testing.

Compression tests and the tabulation of notes from previous studies have shown that certain black and red threads are in consistently worse condition than others. In general, white, grey, beige and other light colours are in relatively good condition. This study confirmed the previously observed fragility of the cotton ground weaves.

pH tests show camelid and cotton have relatively low pH, but the acidity of the fibres is not as severe as was previously suggested and the recent investigations have cast doubt on findings from the previous studies which used a relatively crude pH paper method.

No notable differences in pH range or fibre condition were observed between the collections held in Peru and Gothenburg and those that underwent the ammonium gas treatment.

Differences in condition do not appear to be related to where the textiles have been kept or whether or not they underwent a deacidification treatment but are rather correlated with certain colours and therewith presumably also certain mordants.

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TEXTILES

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